

Menstrual Hygiene Matters: Knowledge, Attitudes & Practices Among Adolescent Girls in Urban Slum of Kolkata Metropolitan

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Abstract

Adolescence represents the critical phase between childhood and adulthood, marked by significant physical and emotional changes. In adolescent girls, menarche - the first onset of menstruation - signals the beginning of puberty, typically around the ages of 12 to 13. Menstruation, a natural biological function, continues until menopause. Historically, menstruation has been surrounded by stigmas and misconceptions, often isolating women and limiting their involvement in social and cultural activities. This study aims to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices concerning menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls residing in the urban slums of Kolkata. A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted among adolescent girls aged 10-19 years in Kolkata's urban slums. With a sample size of 150, data was collected via a house-to-house survey using a pre-designed, pre-tested questionnaire. This survey gathered information on sociodemographic details, menstrual knowledge, patterns, hygiene practices, and cultural restrictions surrounding menstruation. The collected data were analysed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS version 20. The average age of menarche among participants was 12.29 years, with a standard deviation of 1.20, signifying the early onset of puberty. Notably, 57% of participants were aware of menstruation before their first experience, while 42.4% lacked prior knowledge. A significant portion (62.7%) reported facing restrictions, particularly regarding religious activities during their menstrual periods, reflecting the deep-rooted cultural taboos in the community. Only 18% practiced proper disposal of used cloths. Furthermore, 78.7% of the participants used public toilets, highlighting the inadequate sanitation facilities in their households.

Keywords: *Menstrual Hygiene, Knowledge, Attitude, Practices, Adolescent Girls, Taboos, Myths, Urban Slum, Kolkata Metro City.*

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Introduction

Adolescence is a critical developmental stage bridging childhood and adulthood, and for girls, menarche - the onset of menstruation - marks the beginning of puberty (Deshpande, 2018). Menstruation, typically starting around ages 12-13, is a natural biological process that continues until menopause. Despite its normalcy, many adolescent girls worldwide struggle to manage their menstrual cycle in a healthy and dignified manner. To tackle these challenges, Menstrual Hygiene Management (MHM) has become a key area of focus for global organizations like the World Health Organization (WHO) and UNICEF. These bodies are working to promote proper menstrual health practices and infrastructure, aiming to ensure that all women can experience menstruation in a healthy, dignified manner (Singh, 2022).

In India, the vast cultural diversity further complicates the issue of menstrual hygiene. Taboos and myths surrounding menstruation continue to marginalize women and restrict their participation in various socio-cultural activities. For example, cultural and religious beliefs often prevent girls and women from entering temples or kitchens during their periods (Srivastava, 2011).

The United Nations defines menstrual hygiene management as the use of clean materials for menstrual flow, along with access to privacy, soap, water, and proper disposal facilities. However, in low-income countries, there are significant barriers to achieving adequate menstrual hygiene, emphasizing the need for focused attention on this issue. Despite ongoing efforts to improve menstrual hygiene, many adolescent girls still lack basic knowledge and appropriate hygiene practices, leading to poor menstrual health and related infections. This study specifically aims to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices (KAP) of menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls in the urban slum areas of Kolkata, with the goal of preventing gynaecological infections and their long-term consequences (Mishra, 2013; Priya, 2017). By focusing on this group, the research seeks to highlight the need for greater awareness, education, and accessible hygiene resources in these underserved communities.

Objectives of the Study

With the above background, this study was undertaken with the following objectives:

1. This study aims to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices concerning menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls residing in the urban slums of Kolkata.
2. To elicit the beliefs, conception and source of information regarding menstruation among the study population in the slums of Kolkata Municipal Corporation
3. To find out the status of menstrual hygiene among adolescent girls.

Materials and Methods

Type of the Study

A community-based cross-sectional observational study was conducted among adolescent girls aged 10-19 years living in the urban slum areas of Kolkata.

Location of the Study

The study was undertaken among the adolescent girls residing in slums of Borough – VI, VII & XV of the Kolkata Municipal Corporation.

Sample Size

A sample size of 150 participants, was carried out through a house-to-house survey in the urban slums of Kolkata metro city.

Tools for Data Collection

Data collection was facilitated using a predesigned, pretested questionnaire that covered sociodemographic information, knowledge about menstruation, menstrual patterns, hygiene practices, and any restrictions related to menstruation. The questionnaire was refined after pretesting and piloting to ensure accuracy and clarity. Prior to the interview, verbal informed consent was obtained from the parents or guardians, and assent was secured from the adolescent participants. The confidentiality of all responses was guaranteed, and at the conclusion of each interview, the girls received education on menstrual hygiene practices, with any questions they had addressed thoroughly.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive analyses were carried out, and the collected data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS Version 20 to derive insights into menstrual hygiene knowledge, attitudes, and practices among the adolescent girls.

Results

Table 1. Socio-Demographic Profile of Study Participants

Variables	Urban Slum (N=150)	Percentage (%)
Age (Mean)	15.08±1.88	
Age at menarche (Mean)	12.29±1.20	
Marital status		
Married	1	98.70
Unmarried	149	0.70
Education		
Illiterate	16	10.60
Primary	8	5.30
Secondary	100	66.20
Higher Secondary	26	15.90
Socio-Economic Class		
BPL	127	84.67
Lower Middle	22	14.67
Upper Middle	1	0.67

Age

The average age of the participants is 15.08 years, with a standard deviation of 1.88, indicating that the participants are primarily adolescents.

Age at Menarche

The mean age at menarche, marking the onset of menstruation, is 12.29 years with a standard deviation of 1.20. This reflects that puberty generally occurs in early adolescence for the participants.

Marital Status

Only one participant (0.7%) is married, while 149 participants (98.7%) are unmarried, consistent with their young average age.

Education

Regarding educational levels, 10.6% of the participants are illiterate, 5.3% have completed primary education, 66.2% have attained secondary education (the largest proportion), and 15.9% have completed higher secondary education. None of the participants have pursued education beyond the secondary level, indicating a lack of access to higher education within this community.

Socio-Economic Class

The majority of participants (84.67%) fall below the poverty line (BPL), highlighting their economically disadvantaged backgrounds. 14.67% belong to the lower-middle-class category, while only one participant (0.67%) comes from an upper-middle-class background. This demonstrates the considerable economic challenges faced by the community.

Table 2. Knowledge Regarding the Menstruation among the Participants

Variables	Frequency (%)		
	Yes	No	Refuse To Say
Awareness of Menstruation Before Menarche	86 (57.00%)	64 (42.40%)	
Source of Information on Menstruation			
	n	%	
Mother	51	33.80	
Father	0	0.00	
Grand Mother	9	6.00	
Friend	31	20.50	
Aunt	7	4.60	
Teacher	12	7.90	
Sister	39	26	
Other	1	0.70	
Knowledge about Menstruation			
Normal Phenomena	100	66.20	
Illness of a female	12	7.90	
Curse of God	0	0.00	
No idea	32	21.20	
No Response	6	4	
Implications of inadequate menstrual hygiene.	Yes	No	Refuse To Say
	90 (60.00%)	28 (18.70%)	32 (21.30%)
Received information from school regarding menstrual hygiene	Yes	No	Refuse To Say
	28 (18.50%)	102 (67.50%)	20 (13.20%)

Awareness of Menstruation Before Menarche

57.00% of participants (86 individuals) were aware of menstruation prior to experiencing it, while 42.40% (64 individuals) had no prior knowledge. This reveals that a significant proportion of participants lacked essential understanding of menstruation before its onset, underscoring the need for early education.

Source of Information on Menstruation

Mothers were the primary source of information, cited by 33.8% of participants. Sisters were the second most common source, mentioned by 26% of participants. Other family members such as grandmothers (6%), aunts (4.6%), and friends (20.50%) also contributed to disseminating knowledge. Only 7.9% received information from teachers, highlighting a gap in formal education on this topic. No participants identified fathers as a source, and only 0.7% cited other sources of information.

Knowledge about Menstruation

Encouragingly, 66.2% of participants understood menstruation as a natural physiological process. However, 7.9% mistakenly viewed it as an illness, and 21.2% lacked any knowledge about it, indicating a substantial gap in understanding. None of the participants believed menstruation to be a curse, which suggests a positive shift in cultural attitudes.

Implications of Inadequate Menstrual Hygiene

60.00% of participants (90 individuals) were aware of the health risks associated with poor menstrual hygiene. However, 18.7% (28 individuals) were unaware of these implications, and 21.3% (32 individuals) either refused to answer or were unsure, reflecting a degree of hesitancy or lack of knowledge.

Information on Menstrual Hygiene from School

Only 18.5% of participants reported receiving formal education on menstrual hygiene at school. A significant majority, 67.5%, did not receive any school-based information, exposing a considerable gap in the educational system. Additionally, 13.2% refused to answer, and no participants mentioned other sources of school-based education.

This finding highlights a critical need for improved menstrual health education, particularly in schools, to address knowledge gaps and enhance awareness.

Table 3. Attitude Aspect of the Participants

Variables	Frequency	%
First reaction after menarche		
Cried	20	13.33
Scared	34	22.67
Embarrassed	22	14.67
Happy	7	4.67
Told to Mothers	60	40.00
Annoyed	7	4.66
Comfort in School During Menstruation	150	100.00
Attendance in School during Menstruation		
No	6	4.00
Yes	121	80.70
Refused To comment	23	15.40

First Reaction After Menarche

The most common reaction among participants after experiencing menarche was to inform their mothers (40.00%), indicating a strong trust in mothers for discussing personal and sensitive issues. However, many girls reacted with negative emotions such as fear (22.67%) and crying (13.33%), showing that menarche was often met with alarm and distress. Embarrassment was also a notable reaction (14.67%), suggesting that menstruation is still a source of discomfort for many girls. Only 4.67% of participants reported feeling happy about their first period, indicating that positive emotions were uncommon. Additionally, 4.66% of the girls reported annoyance, likely due to the new responsibilities or inconveniences associated with menstruation.

Social Taboos and Restrictions

A significant number of participants (62.70%) faced restrictions from engaging in religious activities during menstruation, reflecting deep-seated cultural or religious taboos. Additionally, 18.70% of participants were not allowed to sleep on a bed during their periods, highlighting beliefs tied to purity and cleanliness. A smaller group (0.70%) were restricted from entering sacred places. However, 12.50% of participants reported facing no restrictions, suggesting that not all are subjected to these social taboos. The 5.40% of participants who refused to answer may reflect discomfort in openly discussing these cultural restrictions.

Figure 1. Social Taboos and Restrictions

Figure 1 illustrates the social taboos and restrictions faced by adolescent girls during menstruation. The data reveals that the majority, 94 girls (62.7%), are barred from participating in religious activities, reflecting strong cultural or religious taboos associated with menstruation. Additionally, 18.7% reported being forbidden to sleep on a bed, likely pointing to traditional practices related to menstrual seclusion. Meanwhile, 12.5% of the respondents indicated that they did not face any taboos or restrictions during menstruation. Only 0.7% mentioned being restricted from entering sacred or religious places during this time.

Attendance in School During Menstruation

A majority of participants (80.70%) continued attending school during menstruation, indicating resilience and perhaps a supportive environment despite menstruation-related discomfort. On the other hand, 4.00% of participants did not attend school during their periods, which could be due to a lack of proper facilities, physical discomfort, or social constraints. The 15.40% who refused to answer may indicate the stigma or sensitivity surrounding the topic of menstruation in the school context.

Overall, this finding underscores the need for ongoing efforts to address the emotional, cultural, and logistical challenges associated with menstruation in these communities.

Table 4. Practice Related Information during the Menstrual among Adolescent Girls

Variables	Frequency	%	χ^2 (P Value)
Menstrual Product Use			
Old Cloths	31	20.67	*0.01
Pads	119	79.33	
Hygiene Practices (Washing and Drying Cloth):			
Cloths Disposed	27	18.00	*0.007
Not Disposed	123	82.00	
Sanitary Pad Disposal			
Refuse to say	27	18.0	1.0
Throw with household dirt	123	82.0	
Frequency of Changing Menstrual Products			
1 to 3 Times	100	66.60	0.9
4 to 5 Times	50	33.40	
Type of Toilet Used			
Public	118	78.70	*0.01
Private	32	21.30	
Access to Facilities in School: Safe Places for Changing Pads			
Yes	104	69.30	
No	46	30.60	
Used Hygiene Kit for washing (Soap/Water)			
No	59	39.30	*0.01
Yes	91	60.70	
Treatment Received			
UPHC	97	64.70	*0.01
Private Doctor	53	35.40	
* P value <0.05 is statistically significant			

Menstrual Product Use

A significant portion of the participants (79.33%) reported using sanitary pads, indicating relatively good access to modern menstrual hygiene products. However, 20.67% still rely on old cloths, possibly due to financial constraints, lack of availability, or cultural norms. This highlights a divide in menstrual product use, with a portion of the population still engaging in less hygienic practices.

Hygiene Practices (Washing and Drying Cloths)

Among those using cloths, 82.00% reuse them, washing them after each use, while only 18.00% dispose of the cloths after use. Reusing cloths can pose hygiene risks, especially if they are not washed and dried properly. The high rate of reuse suggests

both financial constraints and limited awareness about the risks associated with inadequate washing practices.

Sanitary Pad Disposal

Among the girls using sanitary pads, 123 (82%) reported discarding them with household waste, whereas 27 (18%) chose not to disclose their disposal methods.

Frequency of Changing Menstrual Products

The majority of participants (66.60%) change their menstrual products 1 to 3 times a day. This may not meet optimal hygiene standards, as changing products more frequently can help prevent infections and discomfort. A smaller group (33.40%) changes products 4 to 5 times a day, demonstrating better menstrual hygiene practices.

Type of Toilet Used

A large proportion of participants (78.70%) rely on public toilets, which often lack cleanliness, privacy, and security, exacerbating the challenges of maintaining menstrual hygiene. The remaining 21.30% have access to private toilets, indicating that sanitation facilities at home or in the community are limited for most participants.

Access to Facilities in School (Safe Places for Changing Pads)

About 69.30% of the participants have access to safe and private spaces to change pads in their schools, which reflects positively on school infrastructure. However, 30.60% do not have such access, potentially causing discomfort and impacting school attendance during menstruation.

Use of Hygiene Kits (Soap/Water)

A majority of participants (60.70%) use hygiene kits with soap and water, demonstrating good hygiene practices. However, the 39.30% who do not use these kits are at higher risk of infections and discomfort, indicating the need for better access to hygiene resources and education.

Treatment Received

The majority (64.70%) received treatment from Urban Primary Health Centers (UPHCs), indicating that public healthcare facilities are a primary source of care for these adolescents. However, 35.40% sought treatment from private doctors, reflecting either a preference for private healthcare or potential limitations in public health services.

This analysis highlights disparities in access to menstrual hygiene products and sanitation facilities, with gaps in hygiene practices, particularly for those using cloths or public toilets. Improving access to hygiene resources, education, and safe sanitation facilities in schools and communities is essential to enhancing menstrual health management for adolescent girls.

Table 5. Association between Knowledge of Menstruation and Implications of Inadequate Menstrual Hygiene

Variables	Use during menstruation for protection		χ^2 (P Value)
	About		
Knowledge About Menstruation			*0.01
Yes	21 (67.70)	65 (54.60)	
No	10 (32.30)	54 (45.40)	

Implications of Inadequate Management of menstruation			
	Old Cloths	Pad	
Pain during Menstruation	10 (32.30)	59 (85.50)	*0.02
Pain at Lower abdomen	3(9.70)	13(10.90)	
Itching	0	3(2.50)	
Refuse to say	14(51.60)	42(35.30)	
Others	2(6.50)	2(1.70)	
* P value <0.05 is statistically significant			

Knowledge About Menstruation and Use of Protection (Old Cloths vs. Pads)

The results indicate a significant association between menstrual knowledge and the type of protection used. Participants with better knowledge are more likely to use pads (54.60%, or 65 individuals), while those with limited knowledge tend to rely on old cloths (32.30%, or 10 individuals). The p-value of 0.01, being below the 0.05 threshold, confirms that this association is statistically significant, implying that increased knowledge about menstruation promotes the use of more hygienic products like pads.

Implications of Inadequate Menstrual Management and Use of Protection

The data also shows a notable link between implications of inadequate of menstrual management and the type of protection used. Women who experience menstrual pain are significantly more likely to use pads (85.50%, or 59 participants), compared to those using old cloths (32.30%). While factors like lower abdominal pain and itching do not reveal clear preferences for either type of protection, a substantial portion of individuals who declined to comment on menstrual issues use both old cloths (51.60%) and pads (35.30%). With a p-value of 0.02, this relationship is also statistically significant, suggesting that menstrual discomfort or refusal to discuss it may influence the choice of menstrual protection.

Discussion

Knowledge and Attitude

The study reveals a substantial lack of awareness about menstruation among many participants before menarche, underscoring the need for improved education on this subject. Mothers and friends were the primary sources of information, while formal education, particularly from teachers, was notably lacking. Although most participants recognized menstruation as a normal physiological process, some still harbored misconceptions, such as viewing it as an illness. A significant portion also had no understanding of menstruation, highlighting a critical gap in knowledge. While many participants were aware of the health risks associated with poor menstrual hygiene, a sizable minority were either uninformed or reluctant to discuss these risks. Schools were not providing sufficient education on menstrual hygiene, a key area where awareness must be improved. The emotional responses to menarche were predominantly negative, with many girls expressing feelings of fear, embarrassment, or distress. However, the majority confided in their mothers, indicating a strong trust in maternal relationships. Social taboos, particularly those restricting religious activities and sleeping arrangements during menstruation, remain widespread in the community. Despite these challenges, most girls continued to attend school during their periods, reflecting resilience, though some gaps in peer and family support systems persisted. In a similar study conducted in Assam, only 28.24% of adolescents were aware of menstruation before menarche, highlighting the need for more proactive education.

Another study in Jodhpur found that more than half of urban girls used sanitary napkins (Choudhary, 2019). In Chitwan, Nepal, a study revealed that most girls understood menstruation as a normal process, but gaps in menstrual hygiene awareness remain (Neupane, 2020). Furthermore, research in central India showed higher menstrual awareness among private school students compared to government school students (Dixit, 2016) (Paria, 2014).

Taboos and Myths

Cultural and religious taboos surrounding menstruation continue to persist globally. In various countries, myths include misconceptions about tampons breaking the hymen and restrictions on bathing or combing hair. In Poland, having sex during menstruation is believed to be deadly for the partner, while in the Philippines, women are encouraged to wash their faces with their first menstrual blood to clear their skin. In Afghanistan, women avoid washing their vaginas during menstruation, fearing infertility. Such practices, steeped in tradition and religion, perpetuate harmful myths about menstruation. Conversely, in countries like Japan, Brazil, and South Africa, menarche is celebrated as a positive milestone (Ganguly, 2021). In Hindu culture, beliefs about purity contribute to practices like refraining from bathing during menstruation or avoiding contact with cows, based on the belief that it could harm the animal's fertility. These taboos impact not only physical health but also emotional well-being, contributing to school dropouts and creating obstacles for female teachers. To combat these harmful practices, awareness and education are essential from the onset of puberty (Garg, 2015) (Ganguly, 2021). In this study, a majority of girls were restricted from attending religious events during menstruation, mirroring findings from an urban slum study in Delhi where women faced similar restrictions but had relaxed some of them after moving from rural areas due to a lack of social support (Garg, 2001).

Practice-Based Attitude

Although the majority of participants use sanitary pads, a significant portion still relies on cloths, raising concerns about menstrual hygiene management. Reusing cloths, if not done hygienically, poses health risks. The frequency of changing menstrual products is also low for many participants, highlighting the need for improved hygiene education. Most participants used public toilets, which often lack privacy and cleanliness, potentially compromising proper menstrual hygiene. While many schools provided safe places for changing pads, a notable number did not, affecting comfort and potentially school attendance. A majority of participants practiced good hygiene using soap and water, though access to hygiene kits was not universal. Most participants relied on public health centers for treatment, though some sought private care, suggesting a preference for private healthcare or limited access to public facilities. A cross-sectional study revealed that inadequate privacy and basic facilities, such as water and bathrooms, significantly impact menstrual hygiene in resource-poor settings. Addressing this requires improvements in living conditions and the promotion of affordable sanitary pads through social marketing (Dasgupta, 2008) (Prajapati, 2015). A study in rural area of Varanasi found that awareness of menarche was poor, with many girls using old cloths and not maintaining proper hygiene (Kansal, 2016). Similarly, a cross-sectional study in urban slums revealed unsatisfactory menstrual hygiene practices among adolescent girls (Deshpande, 2015) (Boruah, 2022) (Borkar, 2022).

Conclusion

This study aimed to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and practices surrounding menstruation among adolescent girls. While hygiene practices and awareness were generally positive, societal taboos and myths persist. It is crucial to provide education about menstruation before menarche. Notably, most girls continued attending school during menstruation and demonstrated a good understanding of the process. However, there is a significant gap in school-based menstrual health education. Schools must take responsibility for delivering accurate and comprehensive menstrual health education to ensure girls are well-informed and supported. The study underscored that, although there is a reasonably good awareness and practice of menstrual hygiene, several cultural taboos and misinformation persist in the community. Education on menstruation, particularly before menarche, is critically lacking. Despite this, a majority of the girls continued attending school during menstruation and demonstrated a basic understanding of the menstrual process. The study emphasizes the need for schools to play a pivotal role in providing comprehensive menstrual health education. Addressing this gap through structured, school-based programs is essential to ensure that all adolescent girls are equipped with the knowledge and resources to manage their menstrual health effectively.

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